

MEASURING THE ROLE AND EFFECTIVENESS OF FLASHCARDS IN TEACHING VOCABULARY TO EFL LEARNERS.

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Abstract

It is an unrefutable fact that vocabulary plays crucial role in learning a foreign language. To acquire much amount of lexica seems boring and monotonous for students. However, there are many interactive ways to teach words in a fascinating way. Using flashcards in teaching is getting increasingly popular over the world. Flashcards are cards with information on one or both sides, such as words or numbers, that are used in class or for individual study. This article provides with the review of researches that tested the effectiveness of utilizing flashcards in teaching vocabulary sufficiently to young EFL learners.

Keywords: flashcard, vocabulary, EFL young learners.

Introduction

In every foreign language, learning vocabulary is essential; the appropriateness of new terms inspires learners to speak in the target language. Learners are motivated to speak in the target language when they encounter new terms in the language. When learners have a sufficient vocabulary, they have a higher chance of expressing themselves when learning a language other from their mother tongue, according to (Alphonsus,2013 cited in Hussaini et al. 2016). Komachali and Khodareza point out that numerous research have been conducted on vocabulary as a significant component of language acquisition, each of which has made a contribution to the area(2012). Teaching\learning vocabulary efficiently is the key of success in learning language.

Flash card is a phrase or picture on a card that is used to assist pupils learn vocabulary. Flashcards are visual media that encourages the use of the eyes. This type of media displays visuals in the form of symbols, numbers, and thoughts expressed through words and graphics (Herlina & Dewi, 2017 cited in Harisanty et al. 2020). Harisanty and others noted that flashcard games may be a lot of fun and entertaining. The youngster is not aware that he is expanding his vocabulary by using the flashcard game approach. Flashcard games may also be utilized to bring youngsters closer together, as well as children and instructors. Not only is the media approach between children and instructors one of the most successful

media in education, but it is also a visual resource and a strategy to ensure that the learning process for children or students becomes meaningful learning(2020).

Based on this context, the goal of this study is to establish the efficiency of flashcard in the development of young learners information literacy so that policies for literacy culture development may be developed by utilizing flash cards.

Theoretical framework

Flash card is a phrase or picture on a card that is used to assist pupils learn vocabulary. Flashcards are little cards having photographs, writing, or symbolic symbols on them that may be used to recall or guide students to perform anything related to the image (Kupzyk et. Al., 2011 cited in Harisanty et al. 2020).A flashcard is a type of learning material that comes in the shape of a 25 cm × 30 cm image card. The images on a flashcard are a succession of messages delivered as information on each image (Hatiningsih & Adiyati, 2018 cited in Harisanty et al. 2020). The benefit of employing flashcards as a media literacy tool is that they can be carried anywhere and utilized in a variety of ways. New letters, syllables, words, and other information can be drilled using flash cards. They are most commonly utilized in classrooms, although they may also be employed in more informal settings. A flashcard or flash card is a collection of cards with information on one or both sides, such as words or numbers, that are used in classroom exercises or private study. Vocabulary, historical dates, mathematics, and any other subject that can be learnt through a question and answer format can be included on flash cards. Flash cards are a popular learning tool that uses spaced repetition to enhance remembering(Komachali and Khodareza, 2012).

Flashcard are one of the media that may pique the interest of youngsters. Because of its advantages, using flashcards as a learning medium is regarded a particularly beneficial method. The following are the advantages of flashcards: (a) with flashcards, the teacher can stimulate the activities of his or her students in order to carry out the implementation of activities involving the ability in the field of linguistics; (b) with flashcards, the teacher can improve the performance of his or her students in the field of linguistics. Ability of students to practice good and effective communication by implementing language skills in expressing opinions; and (c) with increased individual language skills, they will have no trouble telling a story, and they can improve the quality of the story (Pradana & Gerhani, 2019, cited in Harisanty et al. 2020) . To effectively learn vocabulary, the first point is to to brainstorm ideas, according to Hussaini et al. (2016) practice has the

potential to significantly improve students' understanding in a class. It also makes students interest towards learning to be positive, and this will make them enthusiastic. Students are asked to create a visual representation of the new word to be learned. They can match the word to the picture once they've identified the image. Summarize all of the students' comments without passing judgment. The teacher should entertain all comments from the students.

According to the study's findings of Harisanty and others , flashcard media have advantages and disadvantages, including: (1) being easy to carry anywhere because a flashcard is not large in size; (2) no hassle, where the teacher can use it without having to have special abilities, and if you want to use it, the teacher simply arranges the pictures in the order they appear, and after using, the card can be tied or placed in a special box so it is not scattered; (3) no hassle, where the teacher can use it without having to have special abilities (3) simple to comprehend, because this medium contains particular messages that make it easier for children to comprehend and retain them; (4) because this medium is a game, students can compete according to the rules in order to improve their cognitive talents and inventiveness (Angreany & Saud, 2017, quoted in Harisanty et al.2020).

In the experimental and control groups, Sitompul in his study looked at how flashcards and word lists were used to teach vocabulary. The findings revealed that after being taught with flashcards, pupils' vocabulary mastery increased, and a lexicon. Students in the experimental group acknowledged that they could memorize the words quickly, get more motivated to study English, and comprehend the language vocabulary quickly Students in the control group, on the other hand, thought that making a word list was a time-consuming method(2013).

Hussaini et al. (2016) recommend to language teachers that they can test the efficiency of flashcards in the classroom by creating several phases in which activities can be taught. Teachers should utilize flashcards to divide students into groups and direct each group to conduct different tasks using the new words on the cards (for example: ask them to construct new sentences). Ehri and Roberts (1979,cited in Komachali and Khodareza, 2012) investigated whether first graders learn printed words better in context or in isolation while using flash cards. Context-trained children acquired more about the semantic identities of written words, according to post-test results, flashcard-trained youngsters read the words faster and learned more about orthographic forms. Baleghizadeh and Ashoori (2011 cited in Komachali and Khodareza, 2012) looked at the impact of

flash cards and word lists on EFL students' foreign language vocabulary development. Their findings revealed that there is no significant difference in the efficiency of flash cards vs word lists, as well as partial support for the theory that flash cards may lead to better learning than word lists.

After examining the performance of students in both the experimental and control groups, Shakour and Mehrgan discovered that there was no significant difference between the experimental and control groups on post-testing. At the $p > 0.05$ probability level for the study hypothesis, it was discovered that the observed 1.48 does not equal or surpass the t-critical value of 2.000. As surprising as the outcome of the analysis may be, stated unequivocally that employing flash cards had no impact on college students' vocabulary knowledge (2010).

Conclusion

To sum up the review, flashcards are one of the most effectual ways teaching vocabulary and the importance of vocabulary in learning a foreign language cannot be overstated. For pupils, learning a large number of lexica appears monotonous and uninteresting. There are, however, several interactive ways to teach vocabulary in an engaging manner. Teaching with flashcards is becoming increasingly popular across the world. Flashcards are cards that have information printed on one or both sides, such as words or numbers, and are used in class or for private study. According to many researchers point flashcards improve the proficiency of EFL language learners.

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